

TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION OF ZERO POISSON'S RATIO HONEYCOMB STRUCTURES FOR LIGHTER WEIGHT

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ABSTRACT

This work describes the topology optimization of a zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb structure for morphing skin applications. The configuration of the zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb consists of the conventional re-entrant hexagons and the thin plates located on the thickness direction connecting the re-entrant hexagons as shown in Fig.1. The in-plane mechanics and bending performances of this zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb has been investigated [1, 2]. Comparing with conventional honeycomb structures such as the hexagonal [3], the SILICOMB [4-7], the entrant hexagonal [3], the anti-tetrachiral [8], this zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb design by tessellation of thin plates and hexagons can achieve a separate design of the in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical performances and the largest bending compliance [2]. Honeycombs have been widely used as core materials of sandwich panels in almost every application from cheap doors to advanced aerospace equipment for their remarkable lightweight and tailorable mechanical performances which are directly dependent upon the topology and size of the unit cell [3]. The conventional hexagonal honeycomb structure is a typical example of cellular configurations exhibiting in-plane positive Poisson's ratio (PPR) [9]. However, honeycomb structures with PPR show anticlastic or saddle-shaped curvatures when subject to out-of-plane bending deformation [10, 11]. On the contrary, if the in-plane Poisson's ratio of the honeycomb structures is negative as the re-entrant hexagonal [9, 12, 13], the hexachiral [14-17], and the anti-tetrachiral honeycombs [8], the curvatures are synclastic resulting in a dome-shaped topology [15, 18]. Honeycombs with negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) are also described as auxetic [19-21]. Compared with the conventional hexagonal honeycombs, the auxetic cellular configurations feature increased in-plane shear modulus and enhanced indentation resistance [11, 19, 22]. The bending performances of the honeycomb structures with PPR or NPR constrain their applications in cylindrical morphing engineering [23]. But for the cellular structures with zero Poisson's ratio (ZPR) like the SILICOMB [5, 24, 25], chevron [26-28], and accordion [29], no synclastic or anticlastic can be found when bent out-of-plane. And ZPR also implies that the solids exhibit no lateral deformations when subject to uniaxial tensile or compressive loading. The two special properties make the cellular structures with ZPR performance more suitable for the cylindrical or one-dimensional morphing applications [26, 30]. Nowadays, honeycomb structures have been proposed as a promising solution for morphing skins which is a critical technology for the implementation of morphing aircrafts [31, 32]. Honeycomb structures with ZPR performance have been applied in biomedical scaffolds [33], and one-dimensional spanwise morphing flexible skins [29, 31]. However, it's critical for the honeycomb structures to satisfy the mechanical requests with the lightest weight in aerospace and morphing applications.

Fig.1 Layout of the zero Poisson's ratio honeycombs and the geometry of its unit cell

In this work, we present the multi-stiffness topology optimization of the zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb structures to minimize the weight with stiffness constraints for morphing skin applications using the solid isotropic microstructure with penalty (SIMP) method. Honeycomb structures used in morphing skins as the supporting structures bear not only the aerodynamic pressure but also the aerodynamic induced shear forces. So we do the lighter weight design against the flatwise compressive stiffness and the two transverse shear stiffness of the zero Poisson's ratio honeycomb. The multi-stiffness topology optimization has been done using a norm method with weighting coefficients. According to the results of the multi-stiffness topology optimization, optimized designs have been proposed. And the out-of-plane performances of the optimized designs have also been validated using two ways: HyperWorks analysis with force boundary conditions and ANSYS analysis with displacement boundary conditions.

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